

RESEARCH PAPER

EFFECT OF CONFLICTS ON THE LIVELIHOOD ACTIVITIES OF RURAL DWELLERS IN OWO FOREST RESERVE OF ONDO STATE

¹Ojo, M. O., ¹Aghimien, E.V., ¹Adams, O.T., ¹Areo, Y.M., ²Ade-oni, V.D

¹Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan, Nigeria, ²Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effect of conflicts on rural livelihood in Owo forest reserve of Ondo state. One hundred and twenty (120) respondents were selected from six communities in Owo forest reserve of Owo local government area of Ondo state using purposive sampling and simple random sampling technique. The relationship between personal characteristics such as age, marital status, religion etc and livelihood activities were determined using chi-square. Also relationship between perception of conflict and the effect of livelihood activities were also determined using PPMC as well as the relationship between causes of conflict and livelihood activities. T-test was used to determine the significant difference between, before and after conflict livelihood activities in the local government. From the study, 65.8% of the respondents were married, 55.8% were female, and 59.5% were Christians. The study showed that 69.2% had farming as their major source of income. The study showed that 59.2% had trading as their other income generating activity, 68.3% were non-indigenes, all the respondents (100%) had experienced conflict in the study area and 69.2% agreed that the major type of conflict is for resource control. A significant relationship existed between Sex ($\chi^2=16.153$, $P=0.003$), Religion ($\chi^2=16.153$, $P=0.003$) Educational level ($\chi^2=18.569$, $P=0.002$) and indigene/non indigene ($\chi^2=10.050$, $P=0.018$). Marital status ($\chi^2=3.896$, $P=0.273$) and sources of income ($\chi^2=5.930$, $P=0.204$) showed non-significant relationship. The correlation ($r=0.173$, $p=0.059$) between perception of conflict and livelihood activities was not significant. There existed a significant relationship between causes of conflict ($r=0.443$, $P=0.000$) and livelihood activities. Also the test of difference ($t=0.768$, $p=0.000$) between rural dwellers before and after conflict livelihood activities. Conflict had negative effect on livelihood and the battle for resources was the major cause of conflict. It was also concluded that conflict can be resolved amicably by the parties involved in conflict. It is recommended that proper documentation should be made on conflicts and conflict situation in the study area. Necessary action should be taken to resolve conflict in the study area. Participatory and sustainable approach to resolving conflict should be adopted.

KEYWORDS: Conflict, Livelihood Activities, Rural Dwellers, Forest Reserve, Perception

Received for Publication: 19/02/15

Accepted for Publication: 10/05/15

Corresponding Author: aghimien4@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) considers forest to be land with a tree canopy cover more than 10% which has a larger area than 0.5 hectare and is not specifically under a non-forest land use (FAO, 2001). Other classification systems have used higher canopy cover thresholds, for example defining coverage of 10-30% as 'spars trees and parkland' (UNEP 2002, WCMC 2002). Countries used their own national forest

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournal.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/).

classification system within the threshold set by guidance from the inter-governmental panel in climate change (IPCC) (Penman, 2003). Quality or condition of forests indicates its state of wellbeing with specific information such as tree height, diameter at breast height and species pattern.

Over the past eight years, Ondo State Government has determined to reclaim its various forest reserves, which had led to conflicts. The move, which the government claimed was to secure the future for the unborn generations because the Owo Forest Reserve is one of the reserves that provide significant economic, social and ecological benefits for the citizenry (www.ondostate.forestry.org). The forest play a vital role in protecting the soil; ameliorating the environment and protecting wildlife even the water resources. In most of the forest reserves in the country especially in Ondo state, the government has constituted the Joint Task Force anti Encroachment Unit of Ministry of Natural Resources comprising the foresters, soldiers, police men, State Security Services (SSS) in order to protect the reserves and prevent people from encroachment. This did not go down well with the people engaged in various activities in the forest reserves which have now led to serious conflicts between the people and government because they believe that the move is political. The dwellers are accusing the state government of deliberately ejecting them out of the area without following due process, (www.ondostate.forestry.org). Conflicts over forest reserves and forest resources are ultimately are expression of divergent interests between the stakeholders.

Conflict can include all altercations from those at the household level through those organized or instigated by pressure groups and social movement (environmentalists feminist etc) right up to armed violent conflict, it can occur between communities and higher levels of authority and between national governments. Conflicts are inherent in all societies irrespective of their locations, compositions and mode of organization (Garba, 2002).

Conflicts are used in forest reserves, violet forest reserve conflicts are regular feature of social life in Nigeria. These conflicts result from diverse value system, aggressive competitor for forest resources, encroaching into the set back of the reserve unfaithful and insincerity of the government's agencies, political contributions and unhealthy competition of community leaders. These conflicts arose from degenerated violet stages as a result of poor conflict management (Hassan, 2002). Conflict is part of human experience and to maintain it, it is important to know how to relate with it creatively (Oyesola, 2005). Social structure and institutions can also have a very powerful role to play in the emergence of conflict because they have the ability to mediate, control and fitter social behaviour and altitude. During the last five decades, pressure on forest resources continue to increase, primarily as a result of rapid population growth, unclear tenure system, reliance of forest resources of rural economy and rural livelihood, and subsistence farming. Essentially forest resources in Nigeria continue to dwindle due to clearing for extensive agriculture and shifting cultivation, extensive commercial logging and fuel wood gathering to meet the household energy requirements. Forest resources conflict can damage the relationship between local communities and protected area administration. Examples include the strong community oppositions to the conservation programme in the Selons game reserves, Tanzania (Rose, 1994), and the negative perception of Wildlife conservation held by local communities in Laikipia, Kenya (Gadd, 2005), which later resulted to serious conflict.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

This study was carried out in Owo Forest Reserve, Ondo State in the lowland rainforest of Nigeria. The state is located in the South Western part of Nigeria and lies between longitudes 4.00⁰E and 6.00⁰E and 5.45⁰N and 8.15⁰N. It covers an area of over 15,597 square kilometers. The climate of the state is tropical with two seasons that is the dry season and the raining seasons. The rainy season commences in March and ends in October with a break in June/August with the dry season which occurs between October and March. This means the state lies entirely in the tropics. Ondo state is bounded in the north by Ekiti/Kogi state, in the East by Edo state, in the West by Osun, and Ogun State, and in the south by the Atlantic Ocean (www.ondostate.forestry.org)

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournals.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/).

Purposive sampling was used to select six (6) communities in Owo Forest Reserve namely, Ipele, Molege, Familugba, Ajegunle, Owajalaye, Arajomoeye out of over 12 communities around the Forest Reserve based on information on the area with records of conflicts and displacement. The other unselected communities are Pitch camp, Ilale camp, Mayegun camp, Igbe camp, Ute camp, Elerinla camp. Random sampling was used to select 20 respondents from each community selected making a total of 120 respondents which formed the sample size.

Data Collection

Data was collected using both open structure and ended questionnaire. The questionnaire was in two sections, section one was on the demographic characteristics while the other section was on the respondents activities as affected by the conflicts, its effect on livelihood of the dwellers and the Forest Reserves.

Method of Data Analysis

The statistical tool that was used to analyze the data in the study were descriptive (at the nominal level) and inferential statistics. The former includes tables, frequency distribution, mean, median etc. and this was used to analyze the specific objectives while the later includes chi – square, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and t - test was used to analyze the hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
Table 1: Causes of Conflict by Respondents

Cause	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	SD
Cultural values	42(35.0)	75(62.5)	0(0.00)	3(2.5)	0(0.00)	4.30	0.603
Boundary dispute	69(57.5)	50(41.7)	1(0.08)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	4.57	0.514
Autonomy desire	65(54.2)	54(45.0)	1(0.08)	1(0.08)	0(0.00)	4.53	0.549
Territorial dispute	99(82.5)	19(15.8)	0(0.00)	2(1.7)	0(0.00)	4.79	0.517
Creation of LGA	90(75.0)	30(25.0)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	4.75	0.435
Resource scarcity	96(80.0)	24(20.0)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	4.80	0.402
Property damage	104(86.7)	14(11.7)	1(0.08)	1(0.08)	0(0.00)	4.84	0.449
Concessionaire	98(81.7)	18(15.0)	3(2.5)	1(0.08)	0(0.00)	4.78	0.528

Percentage in parenthesis **Sources Field survey (2011)**

The table above shows that majority of the respondents agreed that sometimes disagreement promote conflicts and breach of agreement can lead to conflict, jealousy also led to conflict in the area, according to the respondents.

Most respondents agreed that conflicts can be resolved amicably, and lead to change in income of respondents. Also it showed that the respondents disagreed that conflict may not be bad. Rent does precedes conflicts demonstration is not a precursor to conflict. This showed that respondents were familiar with conflicts and the resultant effect on people.

Table 2: Mean Distribution of Percentage of Perceived Causes of Conflict

Mean Distribution	Percentage
< mean	41.13
Mean and > mean	58.87

Grand mean = 4.67

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#).

Majority of the respondent agreed that cultural values, boundary dispute creation of local government, scarcity of resources, Damage of property out of concession areas that cause of conflict in the reserve table above shows the distribution of the means response.

Majority of the responding means are the grand means 4.67 hence the response are in affirmation of the cause of conflict highlighted. This implies that conflict is not an issue which just occurs without a factor instigating it. Conflicts have not only heightened the level of insecurity, but have also demonstrated high potential to exacerbate food crisis in Nigeria and other affected countries due to loss of farmers lives, animals, crop and valuable properties. The table above also shows that Mean responses were above the grand mean of 4.67 for positive statement and fall below the grand mean for negative statement. The implication is that the respondents have high perception of conflict as part of human existence and need for it to be resolved to promote their livelihood.

Table 3: Respondents level of Involvement in Livelihood Activities before Conflict

Activities	Always	Occasionally	Never	Total
Cash crop farming	120 (100)	0. (0.00)	0. (0.00)	120
Arable farming	11(9.2)	109(90.8)	0.(0.00)	120
Livestock farming	17(4.2)	103(85.8)	0.(0.00)	120
Pasture crop	1(0.08)	41(34.4)	78(65.0)	120
Hunting	75(62.5)	34(28.3)	11(9.2)	120
Gathering of non	27(22.5)	27(22.5)	3(2.5)	120
Timber product Trading	120(120.0)	0.(0.00)	0.(0.00)	120

Source: Field Survey (2011)

According to the table above, Majority of respondent were into cash and arable farming. This is in line with the finding of (Hassan *et al.*, 2002) that livelihood of most dwellers is farming. Livestock Faming is not regularly involved in it but some were involve. Also pasture-crop, hunting and gathering of non-timber forest product were not regular. Trading were major economic activities involved in by respondent regularly before conflict.

Table 4: Respondent's level of involvement in Livelihood Activities after Conflict

Activity	Always	Occasionally	Never	Total
Cash crop farming	112(93.3)	7(5.8)	1(0.08)	120
Arable farming	120(100.0)	0.(0.00)	0(0.00)	120
Livestock farming	3(2.5)	2(1.7)	115(95.8)	120
Pasture crop faming	0(00.0)	13(10.8)	107(89.2)	120
Hunting	3(2.5)	1(0.08)	116(96.7)	120
Gathering non timber product	12(10.0)	2(1.7)	106(88.3)	120
Trading	120(120.0)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	120

Source Field Survey (2011)

The table above revealed that majority of the respondents where into arable crop while cash crop production which is occasionally e.g. For cash crop: before conflict involve = 120. After conflict = 112, before conflict involvement arable crop = 11, after conflict =120. It was showed that all the activities in the reserve are reduced except trading. This implies that conflict affect livelihood activities after conflict.

Table 5: Chi – Square Analysis of Livelihood Activities and Personal Characteristic of Respondent

Notables	X ²	DF	P value	Decision
Marital status	3.896	3	0.273	NS
Gender	16.153	4	0.003	S
Religion	16.153	4	0.003	S
Other sources of income	5.930	4	0.204	NS
Educational level	18.569	5	0.002	S
Indigene/non indigene	10.050	3	0.018	S

Source: Field Survey (2011)

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#).

There is no significant relationship between rural dwellers and personal characteristics on their livelihood activities in the area. This was analyzed using Chi-square as the statistical tools; the result was presented in the table above. As shown in the table above, χ^2 value of 3.896 and P value of 0.273 indicate that there is no significant relationship between marital status of the respondents, $\chi^2 = 16.153$ and $P = 0.003$ reveals there is significant relationship between sex and livelihood activities. It implies that both male and female lived to fill the impact at effect of conflict in the study area, $\chi^2 = 16153$ and $P=0.003$, shows that there is significant relationship between the religion and livelihood activities in the study area. It implies that religion play important role in country conflict which will later have impact on livelihood activities, $\chi^2 = 18.569$ and $P = 0.002$ showed there is significant relationship between Education level and livelihood activities. This implies that respondent with high level of education has tendency to seek good livelihood activity. It showed in the table above that there is significant relationship between the indigene/ non-indigene and livelihood activities. It implied that both indigene and non indigene determined the nature of conflict.

Table 6: PPMC Analysis of Perception of Conflict and Livelihood Activities

Variables	Correction coefficient	CC	P value	Decision
Perception of conflict Vs livelihood activity	0.173	1.202	0.059	NS

Source: Field Survey (2011)

There is significant relationship between dwellers perception of conflict and the effect on their livelihood activities; this was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The result was presented in the table above. It showed that perception of conflict is not significantly related to livelihood activity. The null hypothesis is accepted which states that there is significant relationship between rural dwellers perception of conflict and the effect on their livelihood activities.

Table 7: PPMC Analysis of Causes of Conflict and Livelihood Activities

Variables	Correction coefficient	Cc	P value	Decision
Perception of conflict Vs livelihood activity	0.443	0.955	0.000	S

Source: field survey, 2011

Correlation test was used in analyzing this hypothesis and the result was presented. It was revealed that there is significant relationship between causes of conflict and livelihood activity. The null hypothesis shows that there is no significant relationship between causes of conflict and livelihood activities of the respondents.

Table 8: T- Test Analysis of Before and After Livelihood Activities

Livelihood activity	N	DF	Mean	STD	SD	T value	P value	Decision
Before	120	119	16.01667	1.47234	0.13441	0.768	0.00	S
After	120		9.32500	0.85172	6.7773			

Source: field survey, 2011

The table above shows that there is significant difference between dwellers before and after conflict livelihood activities. This was analyzed using T – test analysis. There is significant difference ($p=0.000$) in the respondent before and after conflict livelihood activities.

CONCLUSION

The consequences of conflict can be very dire with the rural dwellers. From the study, it was discovered that the effect of conflict on the livelihood activities of the respondents include disruption of agricultural activities, loss of employment, abuse of women and young girls, killing and loss of families.

The study also concluded that majority of the respondents have high perception of conflict hence they perceive conflict as negative from the study conducted. It was revealed that creation of local government, territorial dispute

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournals.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/).

and resource control are major causes of conflicts while change in livelihood was recorded. It was also discovered that conflict had negative effect on the livelihood activities which resulted into decrease in the level of dwellers involvement in the livelihood activities.

Conclusively, the study revealed that conflict can paralyze livelihood activities completely render the dwellers depressed which can lead to health problem and death. However conflicts may be unavoidable, yet they require sustainable livelihood approaches which will guide against the effect while taken care of the consequence sprinkling up on livelihood.

REFERENCES

- FAO, (2001): Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Global forest Resource Assessment. Rome, www.fao.org/docrep/008/10400e/a0400eoo.htm, accessed on 01 January 2007
- Gadd, M. E. (2005): Conservation outside of parks. Attitude of local people in Laikipia, Kenya. Environmental Conservation 32 (1): 50-63
- Garba, (2002): "Conflict in democracy" in Umaru, A.P (ed) 2002: Introduction to Conflict Report in Nigeria, Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, Lagos. Frankad Publisher, Lagos
- Hassan, (2002): Impact of International Trade and Multinational Corporations on the Environment and Sustainable Livelihood of Rural Women in Akwa – Ibom State, Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.
- Oyesola, D. O. P. (2005): Conflict and Comfort of Conflict Resolution. Obafemi Awolowo University Press Limited. Ile-Ife, Nigeria.120pp
- Penman, (2003): The underlying causes of Forest Decline. Occasional paper No. 30, CIFOR, Jakarta
- Rose, L.L. (1994): Dispute in Common Property Regimes (CPRs), Madison, Land Tenure Center, University of Wisconsin –Madison, USA.

